

Simulation of Blood Flow in the Human Arm: A Finite Element Approach

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Abstract:

Mathematical models and computer simulations are increasingly valuable for understanding human anatomy and circulatory system under healthy as well as pathological conditions. In blood circulation through arteries and veins, two key biomechanical processes play an important role: blood flow, governed by fluid mechanics, and vessel wall deformation, governed by solid mechanics. These processes are closely linked and typically must be studied together. The prime objective of this study is to develop a three dimensional CAD model of the arterial network and its Finite Element (FE) Simulation. The arterial walls are regarded flexible to make the simulation more realistic. FE simulation has helped in obtaining the blood flow values at various locations within the artery of the human arm, so that the flow at the radial artery could be estimated with the flow at the aorta. The velocity profile has been generated through the FE simulation. The validity of the simulation has been supported by comparison with the standard published results.

Keywords: Aortic flow, velocity profile, arterial network, finite element modelling

1. Introduction

The field of Finite Element Analysis which is used to analyze various engineering problems in a discrete manner has tremendously increased the human capabilities of understanding and solving complex fluid dynamics domain problems ever since its inception in the early 1940's. The success achieved in the investigation of various engineering fluid flow problems for mechanical, chemical, aeronautical and marine applications has given an impetus to utilize the computational tool in the study of flow involving bodily fluids. The concept of fluid dynamics can be readily applied in better diagnosis and finding faster and improved remedial measures. In the last three decades, tremendous amount of numerical and experimental analysis has been conducted in the bio-medical field involving blood flow to understand the causes of the various diseases and ailments of the human body. In most cases, the artery is modeled as a simple cylindrical tube resulting in approximate solutions. Besides, the pulsatile nature of blood flow has been scarcely studied with the actual cross-section of the artery that is made up of layers of different Young's moduli, densities, and Poisson's ratio.

From the early 1980s, extensive research has been carried out by research scholars in the investigation of fluid-structure interaction involving a flexible, deformable solid. The governing flow equations and numerical models developed during this period and their successful implementation in obtaining the desired results paved the way for research being directed to the bio-medical field.

J. J. Wang and K. H. Parker, 2004[1], calculated the propagation of the arterial pulse wave in the large systemic arteries using a linearized method of characteristics analysis to follow the waves generated by the heart [1]. Jordi Alastruey Arimon, 2006, developed a non-linear one-dimensional model of pulse wave propagation in arterial networks which was validated against a well-defined experimental model and against in-vivo data [2]. Ufuk Olgac et al., 2008, carried out ANSYS® 3D simulation of LDL(low density lipoprotein) accumulation in a human left coronary artery in its healthy and atherosclerotic states [3]. Nanfeng Sun et al. [4] (2008), carried out Computational modeling of Mass Transport in large arteries to study the differences in the characteristic contributions of the transluminal, trans-endothelial and transmural transport towards the proliferation of Atherosclerosis. Emanuel Muraca (2009), investigated a mathematical model of blood flow in carotid bifurcation with the objective to provide a numerical system assessment of wall shear stress [5]. Alin A. Dobre et al., 2010, investigated flow-structural interaction in an arterial branching by numerical simulation [6]. Biyue Liu and Dalin Tang. 2010, performed computer simulations of Atherosclerotic plaque growth in coronary arteries to study the influence

of flow wall shear stress (WSS), blood viscosity and the inlet flow rate on the growth of atherosclerotic plaques using computational plaque growth simulations [7]. J.J. Anza and M.A. Esteves, 2011, performed fluid-structure interaction of upper aorta blood flow, using a hyperelastic Demiray material model[8]. 2D axisymmetric and full 3D models were used along with the upper aorta modeled as a torus with 3 cylinders and the various effects of wall shear stress were studied. Paritosh Vasava et al., 2011, conducted Finite Element Modeling of pulsatile blood flow in Idealized model of Human Aortic Arch to study the effects of Hypertension and Hypotension [9]. Aorta walls were considered as rigid and the results displayed that hypertension causes lowered local wall shear stresses which signifies an increased risk of atherosclerosis. Alexandru Mihail Morega et al., 2011, performed simulations to study the flow interactions in drug delivery through an arterial system using an external magnetic field to attract the magnetisable nanoparticles that, conveyed by the blood stream, carry the chemotherapeutic agents bound to them to desired targets [10].

Jonas Lantz, 2013, modeled and simulated flow in the aorta before and after surgical intervention in an aortic coarctation [11]. Petter Holmlund, 2013, performed Computational fluid dynamic simulations of pulsatile flow in stenotic vessel models to investigate pressure variations within two axisymmetric artery stenosis models and a simplified model of the cerebral aqueduct when being subject to pulsatile water flow[12]. T Guerra and J Tiago, 2014, numerically reconstructed the blood flow circulation inside a real artery deformed by saccular aneurysm obtained from medical images and then imported to COMSOL Multiphysics® to propose a weighted cost function that accurately recovers both the velocity and wall shear stress profiles [13]. Zuned Hajiali ,2014,[14] performed a computational modeling of stented coronary arteries focusing on the stent-vessel wall interactions followed by the blood flow in the post-stenting stage of stenosed human coronary artery. Balazs Albert, 2014, studied and developed mathematical models and performed numerical simulations for the blood flow within stenosed arteries considering Non-Newtonian behavior of blood [15]. Khaled Ben Abdessalem and Ridha Ben Salah , 2015, performed the diagnosis of arterial thrombosis and stenosis in blood vessel using bioimpedance analysis [16]. Abdul Wahab et.al simulated the blood flow through the elliptic and circular arteries with stenosis and observed that the velocity is higher in elliptic arteries [17]. The arteries with stenosis showed higher pressure profiles in the post stenotic regions. Haider et.al simulated the similar stenotic arteries and studied the effect of size, location and shape on the pressure and velocity profiles [18]. Zhang et.al. analysed the effect of tissue stiffness on oscillometric blood pressure , MAP , blood pressure waveform envelope [19]. He et.al. carried out the patient specific numerical simulation of artery stenosis [20].

The literature review has revealed the lack of simulation research conducted pertaining to the study of vascular flow behavior wherein the investigation domain involves an entire arterial tree rather than just a section of the diseased artery which is the case in majority of the past research work that has been performed over the last three decades. The dearth of research in this regard has motivated immensely to investigate the vascular flow behavior for one complete cardiac cycle. This requires the accurate definition of the pulsatile flow waveform by the user in terms of a piecewise function to resemble the systole and the diastole. Also, in order to achieve the objective of conducting a finite element simulation; the decision to adopt COMSOL Multiphysics® as the software to perform the flow simulation proves to be very judicious and perfect.

2. Governing Equations for Blood flow (Navier-Stokes equation)

The flow of blood in the arteries is a 3D flow. Assuming the blood to be a Newtonian and an incompressible fluid, its motion is governed by the Navier-Stokes system of equations (Pletcher,2012). They are derived by applying the three laws of conservation to fluid flow. In component form, these equations can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_j)}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_j \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right) = - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \tau_{ji}}{\partial x_j} + \rho g_i \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + \rho u_j \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} + p \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j} = \tau_{ji} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial q_j}{\partial x_j} + \rho h \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, x_i the position vector components, u_i the components of the velocity vector, p the pressure, τ_{ij} the viscous stress tensor, ε the internal energy per unit mass, q_i the heat flux, h the heat supply per unit mass, and g_i represents the gravitational force per unit volume acting on the fluid, such as gravity forces. The index j indicates the summation over all the components. Eq. (1) results from conservation of mass which states that mass cannot be created nor destroyed; and is known as the continuity equation. Eq. (2) is a set of equations (one equation for each dimension) that describes linear momentum conservation and it states that the rate of change of momentum equals the sum of the forces on a fluid particle. This equation is often referenced as the Navier-Stokes equation. Finally Eq. (3) describes energy conservation which states that the rate of change of energy is equal to the rate of change of heat addition and work done on a fluid particle, and is the first law of thermodynamics. Under transient condition and the assumption of incompressible flow with Newtonian rheology, the flow of blood in the aorta is governed by the continuity and Navier- Stokes equations.

$$\nabla \cdot u = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \rho (u \cdot \nabla) u = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla \cdot (\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T) \quad (5)$$

where u denotes fluid velocity vector and p represents hydrostatic pressure. Also, ρ is the density of blood taken as 1050 kg/m^3 and μ is the dynamic viscosity of blood that is a constant as $0.005 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. The above governing the flow of blood through the larger artery has been modeled and solved using COMSOL Multiphysics software. The following section shows the detailed simulation steps using the software.

3. Geometrical Modeling of the Arterial Tree

The geometric inner and outer diameters used to construct the various branches of the arterial tree model. The geometrical modeling was carried out in Fusion 360® software owing to the various curvatures and differences in the diameters and thicknesses involved in the model. The model was then imported into COMSOL Multiphysics® 4.4 using .sat file format. The 3D geometry for the artery was accomplished using the dimensions sourced from literature [1]: the lumen diameter is 8.66 mm, artery wall thickness is 0.46mm and the total length is 702 mm.

The simulation process is carried out by utilizing two physics modules –the Fluid Flow>Single-Phase Flow>Laminar Flow(spf) module, and; the Structural Mechanics>Solid Mechanics(solid) module.

3.1 Pre-processing

The material properties for the blood and the artery are chosen based on those used in the numerous simulations [5,11,16,22] carried out pertaining to the subject of blood and its interaction with the arterial wall. The density of the blood was taken to be 1050 kg/m^3 with the dynamic viscosity of $0.005 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ (Fig. 1). Similarly, for the arterial wall, the Young's modulus of elasticity was chosen to be 300 kPa , the density selected as 1000 kg/m^3 along with the Poisson's ratio of 0.27 .

Fig. 1 Geometrical model of arterial network in the human arm imported in COMSOL

The outer wall, wall thickness and blood within the artery have been modelled using the 668317 tetrahedral elements, while the lumen has been modelled using 214737 triangular elements (Fig. 2). Tetrahedral elements are the default element type for most physics within COMSOL.

Fig. 2 Mesh generated for the complete arterial tree (Left), Magnified image of the mesh (Right)

3.2 Selection of boundary conditions

The simulation of any fluid flow problem requires the definition of appropriate boundary conditions that govern the flow environment. Typically, they refer to the flow conditions that prevail near the inlet, the outlet and the wall of the conduit.

3.2.1 Wall boundary condition

The wall can be treated as non-porous, since volume transfer of blood in this regard is highly negligible. As such, the blood cannot flow through the wall but rather sticks to the wall resulting in no slip condition, thereby yielding at the wall:

$$u = 0; v = 0 \text{ and } w = 0$$

3.2.2 Inlet and outlet boundary condition

The blood flow which is pulsatile in nature is simulated at the inlet of the artery by pushing it in. To mimic an actual cardiac flow pattern, a pulsatile waveform was developed in MATLAB® through a series of simulation trials until the waveform generated the actual ascending aorta flow rate as shown in fig 3.

The pulse waveform used to obtain the actual systole and diastole phases for a healthy cardiac cycle of 0.8 sec is defined as a piecewise function $f(t)$.

Considering an average heart rate of a normal human to be 75 beats/min, the duration of one beat must be 0.8 seconds. Hence the pulse duration has been considered to be 0.8 secs.

Appropriate boundary conditions play a vital role in simulation based investigation. Due to unavailability of factual data blood flow through the arteries, it was a big challenge to decide the initial boundary condition for velocity and pressure. To overcome this difficulty, a series simulation were carried out. Scaling factor alpha α was used to decide the proportion of the systolic and diastolic peak. The boundary condition which yielded the most appropriate values of the blood flow parameters were

selected for carrying out the simulation.

The pressure, velocity, flowrate and stroke volume have an acceptable value at $\alpha=0.1$, and inlet boundary condition as

Fig. 3 MATLAB® generated pulsatile cardiac waveform depicting Systole and Diastole

3.3 Post-processing

The objective of the FEM simulation was to obtain the blood flow values at various locations within the artery of the human arm, so that the flow at the aorta could be estimated with the flow at the radial artery. Due to pulsatile nature of the blood flow, diminishing radii of the arterial segments and the changing peripheral resistance offered by the network, the pressure and velocity profiles would be different at various nodes of the network. In the post-processing, various parameters such as distributions of velocity, pressure and wall shear stress are obtained in the form of slices, contours, iso-surfaces, etc. and these parameters are plotted at equal intervals of 0.05 seconds starting from 0 s and going the entire range till 0.8 s.

In FE simulation velocity profiles were plotted at $t=0.1\text{sec}$, 0.125sec , 0.15sec , 0.175 sec , 0.375 sec and 0.6 sec respectively.

The peak velocity is obtained at the 0.175sec corresponding to the systolic peak as shown fig. 4 shows.

Fig. 4. Velocity plot for arterial geometry at $t=0.175\text{ sec}$

The velocities as observed in the different branches of the arterial tree during the cardiac cycle are plotted against time in Figure 5. The plot shows the expected trend of decreasing velocity from the Ascending Aorta to the R. Ulnar II artery as the diameter of the arterial tree decreases along the length with the only exception of the R. Carotid artery. This decrease in the diameter along the length offers restriction to the blood flow there by resulting in reduction in flow velocity. The velocity is the highest in the R. Carotid artery due to the abrupt bifurcation and its location near the inlet region. In fact, there is an increase in velocity as we move from the Ascending aorta to the R. Carotid artery. The velocity is the lowest in the R. Interosseous artery owing to its very small diameter and the decreased flow which it receives near the outlet.

Fig 5 Velocity v/s Time plot for inlet and various Outlet arteries

The velocity of the fluid in contact with the wall of the conduit is essentially zero and increases further away from the wall. Generally, it is observed that as the flow area for a fluid decreases, the tendency for turbulence to get generated inside the conduit decreases considerably since no mixing of fluid layers is permitted. A similar phenomenon is observed in the different branches of the arterial tree which are made up of small diameters and this in turn justifies the choice of considering a Laminar flow profile for the simulation. As seen in Fig. 6, the velocity flow profiles are laminar for the complete arterial tree

Fig. 6 Velocity Profile Plot

Flow rate has been calculated from the obtained velocity values and the diameters of each outlet. The blood flow rate decreases downstream along the arterial length since cross-sectional area decreases as a result of reduction in flow diameters from the heart to the wrist. Also, the reduction of velocities downstream also contributes to the decreasing blood flow rate trend that is observed.

The flow rate in the simulation reaches its maximum in 0.175 sec. Thus multiplying this duration (Δt) by flow rate ($\Delta Q/\Delta t$) will yield the stroke volume (ml) i.e. flow at the ascending aorta per beat. The simulation has been carried out for a cardiac cycle of 0.8 sec, thus the heart rate would be $60/0.8$ i.e. 75 beats per minute, where the range of heart rate for a normal beating heart is 60 to 100 beats /min. In order to test the correctness of the simulation, the stroke volume i.e the blood flow out of the aorta per beat, was computed. Cardiac output is another vital parameter which is expressed as the product of stroke volume and heart rate. The stroke volume and cardiac output for the simulation values at the ascending aorta were obtained as 71.57 ml and 5368 ml/min respectively (the range of cardiac output for normal human being is 4000 -8000 ml/min).

The results, obtained using the finite element simulation, were found to be in agreement with the earlier published literature. The simulations carried out by many other researchers were limited to modelling a single section of the artery network but the simulation study carried out in this research has modelled the entire human arm artery right from the ascending aorta up to the ulnar II. Table 1 shows the comparison of the simulation results at the Ascending Aorta (Inlet) with those published in few research papers.

Table 1 Comparison of simulation results with published results

	Velocity (Max) m/sec	Flow Rate (Max) (ml/sec)	Systolic Interval (sec)
Current Simulation	0.6	312	0.35
Frans N. van de Vosse, 2011 [23]	-	300-400	0.32
Guido E. Piele, 2014 [24]	0.6-1	332-498	0.34
Ivor Gabe ,1969 [25]	0.66	-	-

The wall shear stress distribution as observed in the different branches of the arterial tree during the cardiac cycle. The peak value of the wall shear stress at the Ascending Aorta is 2.8 Pa, whereas for the R. Carotid artery in which flow velocities are highest, the wall shear stress peaks to a value of 3.75 Pa. The normal range of wall shear stress in a human artery for blood flow is between 0.5 to 4 Pa [26]. The wall shear stresses obtained in the simulation are below the normal range of 4 Pa for the entire tree. However, clinical evidences suggest that the endothelial cells which line the lumen wall that interacts with flowing blood; have been found to withstand shear stresses upto 35 Pa [27].

The results with respect to velocity and flowrate were evaluated for the entire range of cardiac cycle of 0.8 seconds. The plots for the values of each of the above parameters were obtained at equal intervals of 0.05 sec with the exception of 0.175 sec at which the peak of the systole occurs and hence is quite important to be included in the evaluation.

5. Conclusion

Mathematical modeling of the arterial network of the entire human arm has been carried out right from the Ascending aorta to the Ulnar II artery using Finite Element Analysis. The blood flow parameters such as velocity and flow rate obtained at the radial artery were significantly different from that at the aorta. Imposition of the right boundary conditions has ensured the accuracy of the simulation. The maximum blood velocity at the aorta was obtained to be 0.6 m/sec which is well within the expected value. The velocity profile of the blood flow at various nodes in the simulation is maximum at the center of the vessel and zero towards the walls depicting a laminar flow. By simulating blood flow under various conditions, FEA can be used to identify potential problems like stenosis (narrowing of the arteries) or aneurysms.

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